

DIRECTIONS D2.2:

Report on methods and techniques
for identifying and assessing control
interactions in electrical energy hubs

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Contributors: J. Kircheis, F. J. Cifuentes Garcia, D. Lee, F. G. Puricelli, and J. Beerten.

In addition to publications authored by the contributors listed above, this report includes outcomes of publications with E. Avdiaj, L. Dewangan, and C. Zuromski as first authors.

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Contents

Executive Summary	1
List of Abbreviations	3
1 Tools	4
1.1 Z-tool	4
1.2 PowerImpedanceACDC.jl	6
2 Methods	9
2.1 Passivity sensitivity	9
2.2 Passivity-based design	11
2.3 Current limitation/harmonic filtering	13
2.4 Efficient interaction identification in converter-rich power systems	15
2.5 Robustness and performance analysis of a GFM converter using a parameter-dependent operating point	17
Conclusion	20
Bibliography	22

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the methods and tools developed within the DIRECTIONS project to support the identification and assessment of control interactions in electrical energy hubs. As power systems increasingly rely on power-electronic devices and hybrid AC/DC infrastructures, robust and scalable techniques are required to manage wide-band interactions while respecting model confidentiality and multi-vendor interoperability. The overall structuring of the control-related work in WP2 and WP5 is illustrated in Fig. 1 which organizes the DIRECTIONS control research into four main areas: methods and tools, device-level and system-level stability analysis, and application to relevant case studies. This deliverable focuses on the development of methods and tools, which provide the analytical foundation for subsequent project activities. Device- and system-level control are addressed in deliverable D2.3, while deliverables D5.2 and D5.3 cover their application to relevant case studies. In chapter 2, two complementary open-source frequency-domain analysis tools are introduced. The Z-tool enables automated wide-band frequency response extraction from black-box EMT models as well as small-signal stability analyses, facilitating interaction studies without requiring access to proprietary controller details. In parallel, PowerImpedanceACDC.jl provides an efficient analytical (white-box) framework based on modular component models, enabling large-scale studies and systematic exploration of converter-dominated networks. Together, these tools support the necessary de-risking of small-signal interactions in modern power systems as well as the associated re-design process. In chapter 3, analytical techniques for the identification and mitigation of controller interactions are presented. Overall, this deliverable provides the foundational methods and tools required for the structured control approach adopted in WP2 and WP5, enabling coherent progression from analysis to design and validation across the DIRECTIONS project.

Figure 1: Overview of the DIRECTIONS control approach, with the elements addressed in this deliverable highlighted.

List of Abbreviations

Notation	Description
AC	Alternating Current
CC-GFM	Current-Controlled Grid-Forming
C-HiL	Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DC	Direct Current
EMT	Electromagnetic Transient
EMTDC	Electromagnetic Transient including DC
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
GFL	Grid Following
GFM	Grid Forming
GNC	Generalized Nyquist Criterion
HVDC	High Voltage Direct Current
IBR	Inverter-Based Resource
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
MMC	Modular Multilevel Converter
MTDC	Multi Terminal DC
PE	Power Electronics
PEDIM	Proximal Eigenvalue Displacement Identification Method
QSEM	Quasi-Stationary Electrical Model
SCR	Short Circuit Ratio
VI	Virtual Impedance
VSBI	Voltage Source Behind Impedance

Chapter 1

Tools

To evaluate the small-signal stability of power systems dominated by power converters, versatile and efficient tools accommodating black-box models to protect intellectual property are essential. Frequency-domain methods offer a scalable and modular approach for dynamic analyses which solely relies on frequency response data, thereby not requiring internal component details. However, currently there is no standardized approach for frequency-domain characterization of Electromagnetic Transient (EMT) models. Unlike existing harmonic impedance calculations in commercial EMT packages, which do not consider the dynamic impact of power electronics, electrical machines, and controls, the admittance and impedance matrices for small-signal analysis must accurately capture these characteristics to provide relevant insights into the stability of systems with power converters. Therefore, two openly available tools have been developed: Z-tool and PowerImpedanceACDC. Both packages incorporate several well-established frequency domain analysis functions, and their main difference is that the Z-tool is able to extract the frequency response from EMT models, while PowerImpedanceACDC mostly relies on analytical models. This chapter describes both tools in more detail.

1.1 Z-tool

The Z-tool [1] is the first open-source tool enabling programmatic frequency-domain small-signal stability analysis of systems including black-box models through automated frequency scans of EMT models¹. Fig. 1.1 presents

¹This section summarizes the work published in: F. J. Cifuentes Garcia et al., “Automated frequency-domain small-signal stability analysis of electrical energy hubs,” in *2024 IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Europe (ISGT EUROPE)*, 2024, pp. 1–6 [2], and F. J. Cifuentes Garcia and J. Beerten, “Z-tool: Frequency domain characterization of EMT models for small-signal stability analysis,” *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 252, no. 112405,

Figure 1.1: Summary of main Z-tool functions.

an overview of the Z-tool workflow and main functionalities.

This Python-based implementation interfaces with a custom-built PSCAD library to efficiently extract the frequency response data from EMT models. Contrarily to other methods, the Z-tool can decouple individual subsystems by ideal shunt voltage sources, thereby ensuring their standalone stability which is a pre-requisite for frequency scanning. A subsystem is defined by the electrical decoupling points, for instance it can be a converter, a rotating machine, a DC network, an AC grid and/or a combination thereof. The decoupling points and subsystems are determined by the user-defined connectivity matrix specifying the topology, thus providing total flexibility for the analysis. In particular, it performs subsystem scans via parallel simulations run as independent EMTDC tasks on parallel cores. This makes optimal use of multi-core CPUs and keeps runtime time minimal even for detailed models. In addition, the multi-tone excitation capabilities with efficient FFT processing allows to excite several frequencies at once and extract the frequency response at several frequencies within one simulation, thus reducing total simulation time. The output logging is also reduced to the strictly necessary for the scans so the transferred data to disk is minimized which also improves the overall speed of the tool. In addition, the scans start from a snapshot, where the subsystems are already at steady state, thus avoiding possibly long start-up transients before each perturbation. In addition, the built-in state-of-the-art stability analysis functions, such as generalized Nyquist, determination of oscillation frequencies, node participation factors, etc., allow to effectively analyze the small-signal stability of complex systems including multi-terminal AC, DC and AC/DC power systems with power converters. A complete EMT scan and small-signal analysis workflow is shown in Fig. 1.2.

2026.[3]

Figure 1.2: Z-tool: frequency sweep and stability workflow example.

The Z-tool approach is presented in [2], with particular emphasis on general implementation aspects and its application for stability assessment of multi-infeed AC/DC systems via the case study of an electrical energy hub with a three-terminal HVDC system. Furthermore, [3] introduces more details and enhancements aimed at reducing runtime, such as multi-frequency excitation and the exploitation of symmetry properties, which are tested across various systems. In addition, the usage of the Z-tool to de-risk sub-synchronous control interactions during the integration of an inverter-based resource (IBR) is demonstrated in [3]. Aforementioned case studies and additional examples are publicly available in the Z-tool repository [1]. Lastly, the package has been disseminated with a dedicated webinar, [available online](#), as well as a tutorial covering both theory and hands-on exercises during the 22nd IET International Conference on AC and DC Power Transmission (ACDC Global 2025). Further works demonstrate the Z-tool applicability to analyze small-signal dynamics including internal MMC controls [4, 5], bipolar HVDC systems with grid-forming controls [6], and other cases studies with multiple converters [7, 8].

1.2 PowerImpedanceACDC.jl

PowerImpedanceACDC.jl [9] is a Julia-based framework designed for frequency-domain small-signal stability analysis of white-box power-system

models². In contrast to the Z-tool, which depends on measured frequency response data, this framework is built exclusively on analytical wideband component models implemented directly within the software. Julia was chosen for its high computational performance and extensive scientific-computing ecosystem. By relying solely on analytical representations, the tool achieves substantial computational efficiency and readily supports large-scale parametric studies. PowerImpedanceACDC.jl is the first tool to perform open- and closed-loop frequency-domain small-signal stability analysis using analytical wideband models. Previous tools have primarily relied on state-space formulations. However, as power converters become increasingly prevalent in modern AC/DC grids, state-space modeling exhibits critical scalability limitations. The wideband control characteristics of power converters require accurate high-frequency line modeling, which leads to extremely high model orders in state-space form. Moreover, oscillations may occur over broad frequency ranges, and state-space methods cannot easily restrict analysis to a specific frequency band. Integrating frequency-scan data into a state-space framework is also nontrivial and typically requires fitting routines. Similar to the Z-tool, PowerImpedanceACDC.jl provides state-of-the-art small-signal stability analysis features, including the generalized Nyquist criterion (GNC), oscillation-mode identification, bus-participation factors, and passivity assessment. These functions have been standardized across the two packages. All wideband component models have been validated against their nonlinear EMT counterparts using the Z-tool, ensuring accuracy and consistency. The tool currently includes analytical representations of a wide range of components: two-level converters, modular-multilevel converters, synchronous generators, overhead transmission lines, underground cables, transformers, and generic impedances. Converter models support both grid-following and grid-forming AC/DC configurations with several control modes and follow the modeling described in [11, 12]. Transmission lines are modeled using the frequency-dependent distributed-parameter model, enabling high accuracy at elevated frequencies described in [13]. Overhead-line models allow detailed specification of tower geometry, conductor arrangements, and phase configurations, supporting both AC and DC systems. Cable models describe coaxial structures with up to four conductive and insulating layers, applicable to both AC and DC networks. Transformer models are available in single-phase

²This section summarizes the work published in: J. Kircheis et al., “Power-ImpedanceACDC.jl: An Open-source Tool For Frequency-domain Small-Signal Stability Analysis of AC/DC Systems,” 2026, under preparation [7]. J. Kircheis, F. J. Cifuentes Garcia, and J. Beerten, “Open-source tools for frequency-domain stability analysis of black-box and white-box AC/DC grids,” in *CIGRE Session 2026*, accepted, 2026 [8]. J. Kircheis, A. Gutierrez Martins Britto, J. Beerten, and D. Van Hertem, “Small-signal stability analysis of HVDC cable systems with an open-source cable modeling toolbox,” in *Jicable HVDC25*, 2025 [10].

Figure 1.3: Workflow of PowerImpedanceACDC.jl

and three-phase configurations, with optional delta and star windings, and include high-frequency effects such as lumped capacitances and frequency-dependent winding resistances based on the modeling described in [14]. The overall workflow is shown in Fig. 1.3

Several publications have been prepared to disseminate this open-source tool. In [7], its capabilities are presented in detail, including the underlying modeling framework, two illustrative case studies, and a methodology for incorporating black-box EMT models into PowerImpedanceACDC.jl. In [8], the functionalities of both PowerImpedanceACDC.jl and the Z-tool are demonstrated through case studies in which frequency-scan data from a black-box AC/DC converter model, obtained using the Z-tool, are used to conduct parametric analyses within PowerImpedanceACDC.jl. The ability of the tool to integrate external sources for power-line modeling is highlighted in [10], where detailed cable models generated with the open-source package LineCableModels.jl [15] are incorporated into the white-box modeling framework. Additionally, the package has been disseminated with a dedicated webinar, [available online](#).

Chapter 2

Methods

This chapter presents a set of methods for identifying, analyzing, and mitigating control interactions in electrical energy hubs. The increasing penetration of power-electronic devices and hybrid AC/DC infrastructures in modern power systems motivates the development of advanced analytical approaches. The methods covered include passivity sensitivity analysis and passivity-based control design for grid-forming converters, as well as a computationally efficient interaction-mode identification technique to support small-signal stability analysis of large-scale systems. Collectively, these methods form a coherent framework for the systematic stability assessment of electrical energy hubs.

2.1 Passivity sensitivity

As the increasing integration of power-electronics (PE) converters reshapes power system dynamics, ensuring small-signal stability becomes challenging because conventional sensitivity analysis methods for system design either require full state-space eigenvalue information, which is computationally challenging for large-scale or black-box systems, or rely on approximations that lose accuracy when mode damping is non-negligible. Our work in [16] focuses on developing a generalized passivity sensitivity framework that operates entirely in the frequency domain¹.

The summarized workflow of the proposed framework is presented in Fig. 2.1. The symbols Y^n and Y denote the nodal admittance of the system and device admittance, respectively. Y^n is composed of the admittance matrices associated with active component Y^a and network element

¹This section summarizes the work published in: D. Lee, F.L. Cifuentes Garcia, and J. Beerten, "Generalized passivity sensitivity methodology for small-signal stability analysis," *arXiv*. [16]

Figure 2.1: Workflow of the passivity sensitivity approach.

\mathbf{Y}^{net} . Especially, the network admittance matrix can be calculated by using the branch admittance matrix and incidence matrix, \mathbf{Y}^b and \mathcal{I}_i , respectively. The symbols \mathcal{H}^n and \mathcal{H} are the corresponding Hermitian matrices, e.g., $\mathcal{H} = \mathbf{Y} + \mathbf{Y}^\dagger$ where the \dagger denotes Hermitian transpose.

At the device level, a parametric passivity sensitivity is derived by exploiting the Hermitian structure of the admittance model, enabling systematic identification of which parameters of ρ most influence the non-dissipative frequency regions and in which direction. At the system level, we suggest using a nodal passivity index and demonstrate its less conservativeness compared to device-level passivity approaches. Moreover, the corresponding sensitivity of nodal passivity is formulated through the nodal admittance matrix, accounting for the passivity contributions of interconnected subsystems. The methodology is validated on a single grid-following converter, a three-bus multi-converter system, and a modified two-area system with series-compensated lines and a mixed synchronous generator/converter. The suggested frameworks are confirmed by PSCAD/EMTDC EMT simulations that show a successful identification of the root cause of the dissipative property of system dynamics.

2.2 Passivity-based design

Grid-forming (GFM) converters are expected to provide voltage-forming behavior while remaining stable under weak and varying grid conditions. For GFM modular multilevel converters (MMCs), this is challenging because the interaction between virtual impedance, current control, and grid-forming loops can introduce non-passive admittance characteristics. Therefore, a passivity-based design approach is attractive as it reshapes the converter dynamics to reduce converter-grid interaction risks while preserving the desired system support behavior.

Our work in [17] addresses the challenge that current-controlled grid-forming (CC-GFM) converters, particularly MMCs with cascaded virtual impedance and current control, exhibit non-passive ac-side admittance over a wide frequency range, making them vulnerable to adverse interactions with the transmission grid under varying and weak grid conditions². The electrical model with its control of converter is shown in Fig. 2.2 A key difficulty identified is that straightforwardly enforcing passivity on the MIMO dq -frame admittance conflicts with preserving the "voltage-source-behind-impedance" (VSBI) behavior, which is an essential grid-forming

²This section summarizes the work published in: E. Avdiaj, D. Lee, Ö. C. Sakinic, and J. Beerten, "Passivity-based design methodology for current-controlled grid-forming MMCs," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Industrial Electronics*, pp. 1366–1377, 2025.[18]

Figure 2.2: Electrical model and control of current-controlled grid forming MMC.

functionality. It is shown that increasing the virtual inductance to reduce the off-diagonal cross-coupling term CC^* simultaneously diminishes the required active-power-to-angle and reactive-power-to-voltage responses. To resolve this trade-off, the paper first develops an analytical high-frequency model (valid above 20 Hz) that decomposes the admittance matrix into sub-terms linked to the voltage feedforward, virtual resistance, and virtual inductance, thereby pinpointing the root causes of non-passivity. Based on these insights, a passivity-based design methodology is proposed that combines three simultaneous loop-shaping actions—removal of the voltage feedforward, a second-order Butterworth filter on the virtual inductance voltage path, and a high-pass compensator augmenting the virtual resistance contribution—whose tuning parameters are systematically mapped

Figure 2.3: Comparison of the minimum eigenvalue of $[Y(j\omega) + Y^H(j\omega)]$ for nonpassive and passivated EMT model

Figure 2.4: C-HiL results of weak grid test for different control designs [17].

against the effective impedance requirement to guarantee both passivity and VSBI compliance.

C-HiL experiments and frequency-domain analysis confirm that the passivated converter extends its positive passivity index from approximately 0.7–2 kHz to 6 Hz–3 kHz, maintains the desired instantaneous current responses to phase and voltage perturbations, and achieves stable operation even at very low short-circuit ratios ($SCR = 1.2$) where the non-passive control becomes unstable. The comparison of passivity indices before and after passivation is shown in Fig. 2.3. Fig. 2.4 shows the C-HiL experimental results that the passivated converter is stable while the other is unstable under weak-grid conditions.

2.3 Current limitation/harmonic filtering

Although passivity-based design improves small-signal stability, practical grid-forming converters must also withstand large disturbances such as grid

Figure 2.5: Current limitation strategy.

faults and voltage distortions. In these conditions, the converter current must remain within safe limits while harmonic filtering and passive operation are maintained during normal conditions.

Our work in [18] tackles the practical challenge that passivity-based designs for current-controlled grid-forming (CC-GFM) MMCs, which remove the voltage feedforward to achieve passive inner loops, degrade the current controller's disturbance rejection capability³. For example, it may cause current overshoots that exceed the converter's thermal limits (1.4 p.u.) during grid faults. Simultaneously, emerging grid-side interests require GFM converters to provide harmonic filtering for low-order harmonics (5th, 7th, 11th, 13th) while maintaining passive admittance and ensuring seamless transitions between normal and current-limiting operation. The paper shows that the voltage feedforward, which is essential for fast disturbance rejection during faults, directly conflicts with the passivity requirement, and that existing solutions, such as abruptly enabling or disabling the feedforward, introduce discontinuities in the converter output voltage and fail to keep the current within safe limits. To resolve this, a seamless current limitation strategy is proposed that uses a set–reset latch logic to selectively freeze and unfreeze the internal states of the voltage feedforward low-pass filter and

³This section summarizes the work published in: E. Avdiaj, D. Lee, J. Song, M. Lindner, and J. Beerten, "Passivity, dynamic performance and current limitation of MMC-based CC-GFM with harmonic filtering," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 252, 2026. [18]

the harmonic filtering compensator: during normal operation, the feedforward states are frozen, and the harmonic compensator is active, preserving both passivity and harmonic filtering. The overview of the current limitation strategy is shown in Fig. 2.5. Controller-hardware-in-the-loop experiments on a full-bridge MMC validate the approach under a grid voltage phase jump, a three-phase-to-ground fault, and a single-line-to-ground fault, demonstrating that the proposed strategy keeps the current within the permissible limit and achieves bumpless transitions back to passive GFM operation after fault clearance, whereas the conventional enable/disable approach exceeds current and produces significant voltage transients. Fig. 2.6 shows the C-HiL results of a single-phase fault scenario where the different control designs C1 and C2 are adopted. The proposed control design of C2 shows admissible current responses under the fault scenario.

2.4 Efficient interaction identification in converter-rich power systems

The increasing penetration of converter-interfaced generation complicates stability assessment in modern power systems, as converter-grid interactions span wide frequency ranges and require detailed models with large state dimensions, making conventional eigenvalue-based methods computationally demanding and difficult to apply repeatedly for parametric studies. This section⁴ describes the Proximal Eigenvalue Displacement Identification Method (PEDIM), a selective interaction-mode identification approach that leverages open-loop subsystem eigenvalues, proximity screening, and displacement analysis under incremental coupling to efficiently detect interaction modes without computing the full closed-loop spectrum. The method combines an eigenvalue proximity criterion, a displacement criterion based on eigenvalue sensitivity, and a reduced-order state-variable formulation to significantly reduce computational effort while preserving accuracy in identifying dominant interactions. Fig. 2.7 illustrates the flow chart of the proposed PEDIM.

Applied to a four-terminal MTDC system and a modified IEEE 39-bus system, PEDIM successfully identifies key interaction modes and accurately estimates their closed-loop evolution, matching the results of traditional QZ-based modal analysis while requiring substantially less computation time, up to 40% faster in a study considering a large-scale system with over 1,000 states [19]. The results demonstrate that PEDIM provides a modular,

⁴This section summarizes the work published in: L. Dewangan, F. G. Puricelli, and J. Beerten, "Interaction assessment of converter-interfaced power systems using proximal eigenvalue displacement approach," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, pp. 1–14, 2026. [19]

Figure 2.6: C-HiL results of single-phase fault scenario for different control designs [18].

Figure 2.7: Flow chart of the proposed PEDIM [19].

scalable, and computation-efficient framework for detecting converter-grid interactions, supporting stability assessment even in systems with black-box converter models and multi-vendor architectures.

2.5 Robustness and performance analysis of a GFM converter using a parameter-dependent operating point

Converter-dominated power systems might require grid-forming (GFM) converters to remain stable under uncertain and changing grid conditions, yet conventional robustness tools struggle to account for nonlinear operating-point shifts caused by parameters such as the short-circuit ratio (SCR). Our work⁵ in [20] addresses this challenge by analyzing the robustness of a current-controlled quasi-stationary electrical-model virtual impedance (CC-QSEM VI) of the virtual synchronous machine (VSM), showing that classical uncertainty analysis (μ -analysis) can provide misleading conclusions when operating-point variations induced by uncertainties are neglected. To overcome this limitation, we propose a robustness-assessment framework based on parameter-dependent operating points combined with symbolic linearization, enabling the linearized model to explicitly capture how grid and control parameter uncertainties influence the operating point. This approach avoids repeated relinearization during parameter sweeps and allows efficient eigenvalue-based robustness studies across wide uncertainty

⁵This section summarizes the work published in: C. Zuromski, F. G. Puricelli, J. Beerten, and C. Becker, “Robustness and performance analysis of a current-controlled quasi-stationary electrical model virtual synchronous machine using a parameter-dependent operating point,” *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 1–15, 2026 [20].

ranges. The results in Fig. 2.8 illustrate that system robustness is mainly impacted by parameters related to the QSEM VI, and that appropriate tuning, specifically, higher virtual inductance, lower QSEM VI low-pass-filter bandwidth, and reduced current-control bandwidth, significantly improves stability margins under SCR variations, enabling stable operation down to $\text{SCR} \approx 0.75$ in the studied case. Particularly, to evaluate how the low-pass filter bandwidth ω_{vf} influences system robustness under grid uncertainties, a range of bandwidth values ω_{vf} from 30 rad/s to 600 rad/s is examined. Grid uncertainties are represented by varying the short-circuit ratio (SCR) between 0.5 and 10. Fig. 2.8 (a) illustrates the system's stability boundary as a function of both SCR and ω_{vf} . The results indicate that increasing the filter bandwidth reduces stability in weaker grids. For instance, when the bandwidth exceeds 200 rad/s, the system remains stable only if the grid is sufficiently strong, specifically with an SCR greater than 4.5. Fig. 2.8 (b) clearly illustrates how system stability depends on the virtual inductance l_s , which is varied between 0.1 p.u. and 0.5 p.u. Lower values of l_s noticeably shrink the stable operating region. This effect is particularly pronounced in weak grids, where higher values of l_s are necessary to preserve system stability. Finally Fig. 2.8 (c) shows how the robustness of the converter to uncertain SCRs changes for different current controller bandwidths, considering $\omega_{\text{bw,cc}}$ between $2\pi 50$ and $2\pi 250$, and indicating that a smaller current control bandwidth increases the stability region in weaker systems. In [20], complementary sensitivity-function analysis further shows that parameter sets that enhance robust stability also preserve good active-power tracking and angle-disturbance rejection. Overall, the proposed method offers a computationally efficient and reliable robustness-evaluation framework for GFM converter controls in systems where nonlinear operating-point dependence is non-negligible.

(a) Influence of ω_{vf} with $l_s = 0.25$ pu and $\omega_{bw,cc} = 2\pi \cdot 150$ rad/s.

(b) Influence of l_s with $\omega_{vf} = 200$ rad/s and $\omega_{bw,cc} = 2\pi \cdot 150$ rad/s.

(c) Influence of $\omega_{bw,cc}$ with $l_s = 0.25$ pu and $\omega_{vf} = 200$ rad/s.

Figure 2.8: Stability limits as a function of the SCR, considering the effects of the QSEM VI low-pass filter bandwidth ω_{vf} , the QSEM VI inductance l_s , and the current control bandwidth $\omega_{bw,cc}$ [20].

Conclusion

In this deliverable, a comprehensive set of methods and tools developed within the DIRECTIONS project to support the identification, assessment and mitigation of control interactions in electrical energy hubs is presented. As power systems transition towards converter-dominated architectures with increasing penetration of hybrid AC/DC infrastructures, conventional stability analysis and control-design approaches face fundamental limitations in terms of scalability, confidentiality, and applicability across wide frequency ranges.

At the tooling level, the Z-tool and PowerImpedanceACDC.jl together enable a flexible and consistent workflow across different modeling frameworks. The Z-tool facilitates automated frequency-domain characterization and stability analysis primarily based on EMT models without requiring access to internal model parameters, whereas PowerImpedanceACDC.jl leverages the a computational efficiency of analytical wideband component models for large-scale parametric studies. Their complementary nature allows for the integration of black-box EMT models with analytical power system models to allow for fast small-signal stability assessment.

Additionally, a range of analytical methods for understanding and mitigating control interactions has been developed. Passivity sensitivity analysis provides principled guidance for identifying the parameters and subsystems that most strongly influence interaction risks, enabling targeted and physically interpretable control adjustments. Passivity-based control design methodologies for grid-forming converters demonstrate how robust interaction behavior can be achieved without sacrificing essential grid-forming functionalities. Practical extensions addressing current limitations and harmonic filtering further ensure that passivity-oriented design remains compatible with operational demands. In addition, new modeling and analysis techniques have been introduced to address system-level challenges. The proposed interaction-mode identification reduces the computational burden associated with the stability assessment in converter-rich power systems. Lastly, the proposed robustness-evaluation framework, applied to a grid-forming converter, enables computationally efficient and reliable robustness analysis while accounting for operating-point dependency.

Overall, the methods and tools presented in this deliverable form the analytical foundation for the structured control approach adopted in the DIRECTIONS project. They enable systematic progression from interaction identification to mitigation and robust control design, and provide the basis for device-level and system-level studies addressed in subsequent deliverables. By combining scalability, transparency, and practical relevance, this work contributes to the development of reliable, interoperable, and resilient control solutions for future electrical energy hubs.

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